

An efficient method for solving infinite horizon optimal control problems

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Abstract

In this paper, an efficient method for numerical solution of infinite horizon optimal control problems is presented. In the proposed method, we construct the Rational Bobaker functions and the derivative operational matrix of these functions for the first time. Then they are used to reduce the problem to that of solving a system of algebraic equations. The main advantages of the present method are obtaining good results, while the infinite horizon problem is solved on the original time interval of the problem without transforming it to a finite one.

Keywords: Optimal control, Infinite horizon problems, Rational Boubaker function

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1 Introduction

Optimal control problems with infinite horizon appear in some of the well-known areas of application, such as, management science and economics, aerospace engineering, chemical reaction systems, and biology. Such problems are described on an infinite time domain, $[0, \infty)$. It is noted that, in most of the existing works, an infinite horizon optimal control problem is approximated with a finite horizon problem by using a change of variable. The aim of this paper is to present a method for an efficient solution of optimal control problems with infinite horizon. For this purpose, at first, an appropriate finite or discrete representation of the solution of the problem which is based on Rational Boubaker functions, is determined. Next, the infinite horizon optimal control problem is transcribed to a mathematical problem by using this discrete representation of the solution and collocating the differential equations on the transformed Legendre-Gauss-Radau (TLGR) points. Our method, unlike most of the existing works, has the property that, it does not require any change of variable to map the domain of the infinite time interval of the problem to a finite time interval. Instead, by using the transformed functions, the infinite horizon optimal control problem is solved on the original

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time interval (semi-infinite interval) of the problem. This paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, a formulation for Rational Boubaker functions and also the operational matrix of derivative are introduced. In Section 3, we discuss the mentioned problem and the proposed method. In Section 4, the proposed method is applied on numerical examples arising in the optimal control theory and the advantages of our method are shown. Finally we give a brief explanation in conclusion part.

2 Rational Boubaker functions

In this part of paper, the Boubaker polynomials are recalled, then we construct the Rational Boubaker functions and their derivative operational matrix.

The explanation of the Boubaker polynomials is

$$B_0(t) = 1,$$

$$B_i(t) = \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} (-1)^r \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i-4r}{i-r} t^{i-2r}, \quad i \geq 1,$$

where the symbol $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ depicts the floor function. These polynomials can be written as [4]

$$B_{2k}(t) = 2T_{2k}(t/2) + 8T_{2k-2}(t/2) + 8T_{2k-4}(t/2) + \dots + 8T_2(t/2) + 2T_0(t/2), \quad (1)$$

$$B_{2k+1}(t) = 2T_{2k+1}(t/2) + 8T_{2k-1}(t/2) + 8T_{2k-3}(t/2) + \dots + 8T_3(t/2) + 8T_1(t/2). \quad (2)$$

We set

$$\Psi(t) = \Lambda \phi(t/2),$$

where $\Psi(t)$ and $\phi(t)$ are the following Boubaker polynomials vector and the Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind vector, respectively and Λ is an $(m+1) \times (m+1)$ matrix obtained from Eqs (1) and (2).

$$\Psi(t) = [B_0(t), B_1(t), \dots, B_m(t)]^T, \quad \phi(t) = [T_0(t), T_1(t), \dots, T_m(t)]^T.$$

Now we define Rational Boubaker functions as

$$RB_i(t) = B_i\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right),$$

so the Rational Boubaker functions vector can be expressed as

$$\Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right) = \Lambda \phi\left(\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right),$$

where $\phi\left(\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right)$, is the Rational Chebyshev functions vector.

2.1 The operational matrix of Rational Boubaker functions

Here we construct the derivative operational matrix of Rational Boubaker functions. For this purpose we consider

$$D\Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right) = \Lambda D\phi\left(\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right),$$

D shows the derivative operator and we have

$$D\phi\left(\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right) = \Theta\phi\left(\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right),$$

where Θ is the derivative operational matrix of Rational Chebyshev functions introduced in [5]. As a result the operational matrix of Rational Boubaker functions Ω could be constructed as

$$D\Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right) = \Omega\Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right),$$

which can be calculated as $\Omega = \Lambda.\Theta.\Lambda^{-1}$.

3 Problem statement

In this paper, the following class of optimal control problems is considered. The problem is to find a control vector $u(t) = [u_1(t), \dots, u_q(t)]^T$, and the corresponding state vector $x(t) = [x_1(t), \dots, x_p(t)]^T$, which minimize the functional

$$\min J(x, u) = \int_0^\infty g(x(t), u(t))dt,$$

subject to a system of p differential equations

$$Dx_k(t) = f_k(x(t), u(t)), \quad k = 1, \dots, p,$$

with the initial conditions

$$x_k(0) = \mu_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, p,$$

$Dx_k(t)$ denotes the time derivative of $x_k(t)$.

To solve this infinite horizon optimal control problem, at first, the functional J is discretized using the transformed Legendre-Gauss-Radau (TLGR) quadrature as follows

$$\bar{J} = \int_0^\infty g(x(t), u(t))dt \simeq \sum_{i=0}^m g(x_m(t_i), u_m(t_i)) \frac{\varpi_i}{\omega(t_i)},$$

where ϖ_i are the corresponding weights with $(m+1)$ TLGR points [1]. $x_m(t)$ and $u_m(t)$ are the approximations of $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ as

$$x_m(t) = [x_{1,m}(t), \dots, x_{p,m}(t)]^T, \quad u_m(t) = [u_{1,m}(t), \dots, u_{q,m}(t)]^T,$$

in which

$$x_{k,m}(t) \simeq A_k^T \Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right) \quad u_{s,m}(t) \simeq B_s^T \Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right).$$

Also $A_k, k = 1, \dots, p$ and $B_s, s = 1, \dots, q$ are unknown coefficient vectors. Now by substituting these approximation in problem we set

$$H_k(t) = A_k^T \Omega \Psi\left(2\frac{t-L}{t+L}\right) - f_k(x_m(t), u_m(t)),$$

and

$$J^* = \bar{J} + \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{f=0}^m H_k(t_f) \lambda_{k,f} + \sum_{k=1}^p (x_k(0) - \mu_k) \gamma_k,$$

where γ_k and $\lambda_{k,f}$, are unknown Lagrange multipliers and $t_f, f = 0, \dots, m$ are TLGR collocation points. The necessary conditions for finding the extreme of J^* , are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial A_k} &= 0, \quad k = 1, \dots, p, & \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial B_s} &= 0, \quad s = 1, \dots, q, \\ \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \lambda_{k,f}} &= 0, \quad k = 1, \dots, p, \quad f = 0, \dots, m, & \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \gamma_k} &= 0, \quad k = 1, \dots, p, \end{aligned}$$

This system should be solved by numerical algorithms and then by replacing the obtained values from this system $u(t)$ and $x(t)$ can be calculated.

4 Main results

In this section, we solve an infinite horizon control of a two-dimensional system and a nonlinear one to show the accuracy of proposed method.

Example 1: Consider the following problem [2]

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} \left(x_1^2(t) + \frac{1}{2}x_2^2(t) + \frac{1}{4}u^2(t) \right) dt,$$

s.t

$$Dx_1(t) = x_2(t),$$

$$Dx_2(t) = 2x_1(t) - x_2(t) + u(t),$$

and initial conditions

$$x_1(0) = -4, \quad x_2(0) = 4.$$

The exact solution of this problem is $J = 19.8533565649837$. Table 1 shows the estimated values of J for different m and the absolute errors between the exact value of cost function and the numerical one. As

Table 1: The estimated values of J and absolute errors for Example 1.

m	J	errors of J
5	19.8898	3.64×10^{-2}
10	19.85378	4.24×10^{-4}
15	19.85336	7.54×10^{-6}
20	19.85335	1.67×10^{-7}
25	19.853356	4.64×10^{-8}

we can see from Table 1, the numerical values of cost function are convergent to the exact value and the absolute errors are decreased as m is increased.

Example 2: Consider the following problem [3]

$$J = 1/2 \int_0^{\infty} \left(\ln^2 x(t) + u^2(t) \right) dt,$$

s.t

$$Dx(t) = x(t) \left(\ln x(t) + u(t) \right),$$

and initial condition

$$x(0) = e^2.$$

The exact value of J for this problem is $J = 4.82842712474619$.

Table 2: The estimated values of J and absolute errors for Example 2.

m	J	errors of J
5	4.83151	3.08×10^{-3}
10	4.828471	4.38×10^{-5}
15	4.828428	1.26×10^{-6}
20	4.82884278	7.08×10^{-7}
25	4.82884271	8.75×10^{-9}

Table 2 shows the numerical values of J and the absolute errors for different m . It is shown that by increasing m , the more accurate numerical results are achieved.

5 Conclusion

In the present work, transformed Boubaker functions are introduced. These functions with a spectral method are applied to transcribe infinite horizon optimal control problems to a system of algebraic equations which can be solved by the numerical iterative methods. Our method has the property that, the original problem is solved on the semi-infinite interval without transforming it to a finite interval. In addition, good results are obtained and the rate of convergence is high.

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